

Synthesis and *in vitro* antifungal activity of some azomethines

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Abstract : A new series of azomethines were synthesized by condensation of different sulphonamide derivatives with substituted aromatic aldehydes containing allyl and allyloxy group. The structures of these products were confirmed by physical and spectral analysis. The compounds were assayed for antifungal activity against different human pathogens such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus*. All the compounds exhibited considerable inhibition against the fungi tested.

Keywords : Antifungal screening, azomethines, disc diffusion.

Introduction

The increase in the mortality rate associated with infectious diseases is directly related to fungi that exhibit multiple resistance to antibiotics. The lack of effective treatments is the main cause of this problem^{1,2}. The development of new antifungal agents with novel and more efficient mechanisms of action is definitely an urgent medical need³. Azomethine are some of the most widely used organic compounds. Sulfonamide derivatives have been subject to intensive studies, where a wide variety of those derivatives have been prepared and used in various biological and pharmacological fields. Azomethines are among the most studied sulfonamide derivatives which have been used for numerous biological applications^{4,5}.

These types of derivatives are very important because of their varied structures and biological activities^{6,7}. They are the important compound owing to their wide range of biological activities and industrial application. They have been found to possess the pharmacological activities such as antimicrobial⁸⁻¹³, antipathogenic^{14,15}, antidepressant¹⁶, antiviral^{17,18}, anticancer^{19,20}, fungicide^{21,22}, bactericide^{23,24}, cytotoxicity²⁵, herbicide²⁶, insecticide^{27,28}, antioxidant agent^{29,30}, antiproliferative^{31,32}.

The development of fungal resistance to existing drugs is a major problem in antifungal therapy and necessitates continuing research into new classes of antifungals. It is evident that in azomethine derivatives the C=N linkage

is an essential structural requirement for biological activity. These compounds are readily hydrolyzed under acidic conditions leading to active aldehydes which can act as alkylating agents. Many attempts have been made to synthesize, characterize and to study biological activity of azomethine. In view of the conclusions drawn from the previous work and looking to the antimicrobial efficacy of sulphonamides like sulphanilamide, sulphamethoxazole, sulphathiazole and sulphadimidine moieties attached to aryl ring it seems logical to combine all these moieties together in a parent molecule. This study was aimed at exploring the potential antifungal compounds containing an azomethine group (-CH=N).

Materials and methods :

Chemistry :

All chemicals and solvents, reagents used in the present study were of analytical grade and solvents were used after distillation. All the melting points of the synthesized compounds were determined by open capillary and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked using precoated TLC plates (MERCK) using *n*-hexane : ethyl acetate (8 : 2) solvent system. The developed chromatographic plates were visualized under UV at 254 nm. IR spectra were recorded using KBr on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra in DMSO on a BRUKER FT-NMR instrument using TMS as internal standard and chemical shift values were expressed in ppm.

Elemental analysis (CHN) was performed on Carlo Erba 1108.

Our general synthetic route leading to new azomethines involved the reaction between aromatic aldehydes containing allyl and allyloxy group with different sulphonamide derivatives is shown in Scheme 1.

General procedure for the synthesis of azomethines :

A solution of substituted aromatic aldehydes (0.01 M : 5 mL ethanol) was taken in a flask and sulphonamide derivatives (0.01 M : 5 mL ethanol) was slowly added with continuous stirring. The contents of the flask were refluxed for three hours and left over night. The reaction mixture was cooled in an ice bath and a drop of sulfuric acid was added to it. The azomethines base separated out, collected and further purified by recrystallization from ethanol.

4-[(E)-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)methylidene]amino}benzenesulfonamide (1a) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : C₁₄H₁₄N₂O₄S; Mol. wt. 306; yield 58%; m.p. 200 °C; colour : whitish yellow;

low; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3400 (O-H), 1670 (CH=N), 1139 (S=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ, ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 2.2 (2H, s, SO₂NH₂). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 54.90; H, 4.60; N, 9.12; O, 20.91; S, 10.47.

4-[(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-N-(1,3-thiazol-2-yl)benzenesulfonamide (1b) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : C₁₇H₁₅N₃O₄S₂; Mol. wt. 389; yield 72%; m.p. 150 °C; colour : yellow; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3420 (O-H), 1650 (CH=N), 1115 (S=O); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ, ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO₂NH), 6.5–7.5 (2H, m, CH). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 52.40; H, 3.91; N, 10.70; O, 16.52; S, 16.47.

4-[(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-N-(5-methylisoxazol-2-yl)benzenesulfonamide (1c) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : C₁₈H₁₇N₃O₅S; Mol. wt. 387; yield 98%; m.p. 190 °C; colour : pale yellow;

Where R' = (1)p-OH,
(2)p-CH₂=CH-OCH₂, o-NO₂
(3)p-OH, m-CH₂=CH-CH₂,

R'' = (a)H (Sulphanilimide)

Scheme 1. General scheme of the reaction.

IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3440 (O-H), 1670 (CH=N), 1149 (S=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO_2NH), 5.2 (1H, s, CH), 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 52.30; H, 4.01; N, 10.70; O, 16.52; S, 16.47.

N-(4,6-Dimethylpyrimidin-2-yl)-4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)methylidene]amino}benzenesulfonamide (**1d**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}$; Mol. wt. 412 ; yield 50%; m.p. 110 °C; colour : yellow; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3450 (O-H), 1660 (CH=N), 1153 (S=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO_2NH), 3.8 (1H, s, CH), 2.8–3.0 (6H, s, CH_3). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 58.20; H, 4.93; N, 13.50; O, 15.60; S, 7.77.

4-[(5-Methoxy-2-nitro-4-vinylloxymethyl-benzylidene)-amino]-benzenesulfonamide (**2a**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6\text{S}$; Mol. wt. 391; yield 66%; m.p. 120 °C; colour : yellow ; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1617 (CH=N), 1598 (NO_2), 1139 (S=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 5.2–7.2 (2H, m, Ar-H), 5.4 (2H, s, CH), 6.5 (1H, t, CH), 4.2 (2H, d, CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (2H, s, SO_2NH_2). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 52.00; H, 4.55; N, 10.70; O, 24.57; S, 8.19.

4-[(5-Methoxy-2-nitro-4-vinylloxymethyl-benzylidene)-amino]-*N*-thiazol-2-yl-benzenesulfonamide (**2b**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$; Mol. wt. 474; yield 70%; m.p. 110 °C; colour : brown yellow; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1627 (CH=N), 1588 (NO_2), 1190 (S=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 5.2–7.2 (2H, m, Ar-H), 5.4 (2H, s, CH), 6.5 (1H, t, CH), 4.2 (2H, d, CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO_2NH), 6.5–7.5 (2H, m, CH). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 50.30; H, 3.82; N, 11.81; O, 20.55; S, 13.51.

N-(4,6-Dimethyl-pyrimidin-2-yl)-4-[(5-methoxy-2-nitro-4-vinylloxymethyl-benzylidene)-amino]benzenesulfonamide (**2c**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_5\text{O}_6\text{S}$; Mol. wt. 520 ; yield 60%; m.p. 130 °C; colour : brown yellow; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1620 (CH=N), 1542 (NO_2), 1139 (S=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH),

5.2–7.2 (3H, m, ArH), 5.4 (2H, s, CH), 6.5 (1H, t, CH), 2.0 (2H, d, CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO_2NH), 3.8 (1H, s, CH), 2.8–3.0 (6H, s, CH_3). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 55.50; H, 4.68; N, 14.00; O, 19.37; S, 6.44.

4-[(4-Allyloxy-5-methoxy-2-nitro-benzylidene)-amino]-*N*-(5-methyl-isoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (**2d**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7\text{S}$; Mol. wt. 472 ; yield 70%; m.p. 120 °C; colour : brown yellow; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 1640 (CH=N), 1540 (NO_2), 1120 (S=O); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 5.2–7.2 (2H, m, Ar-H), 5.4 (2H, s, CH), 6.5 (1H, t, CH), 4.2 (2H, d, CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO_2NH), 5.2 (1H, s, CH), 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 53.30; H, 4.35; N, 11.80; O, 23.76; S, 6.79.

4-[(3-Allyl-4-hydroxy-5-methoxy-benzylidene)-amino]-benzenesulfonamide (**3a**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$; Mol. wt. 346; yield 72%; m.p. 75 °C; colour : yellow; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3430 (O-H), 1630 (CH=N); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (2H, m, Ar-H), 4.96 (2H, d, CH), 6.4 (1H, p, CH), 3.5 (2H, d, CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 2.2 (2H, s, SO_2NH_2). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 58.90; H, 5.28; N, 8.09; O, 18.47; S, 9.27.

4-[(3-Allyl-4-hydroxy-5-methoxy-benzylidene)-amino]-*N*-thiazol-2-yl-benzenesulfonamide (**3b**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{S}$; Mol. wt. 429; yield 80%; m.p. 65 °C; colour : cremish yellow; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3410 (O-H), 1650 (CH=N); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (2H, m, Ar-H), 4.96 (2H, d, CH), 6.4 (1H, p, CH), 3.5 (2H, d, CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO_2NH), 6.5–7.5 (2H, m, CH). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 55.90; H, 4.49; N, 9.70; O, 14.98; S, 14.93.

4-[(3-Allyl-4-hydroxy-5-methoxy-benzylidene)-amino]-*N*-(5-methyl-isoxazol-3-yl)benzenesulfonamide (**3c**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}$; Mol. wt. 427; yield 95%; m.p. 70 °C; colour : cremish white; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3400 (O-H), 1670 (CH=N); ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ , ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (2H, m, Ar-H), 4.96 (2H, d, CH), 6.4 (1H, p, CH), 3.5 (2H, d, CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH),

CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO₂NH), 5.2 (1H, s, CH), 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 59.00; H, 4.98; N, 9.80; O, 18.70; S, 7.51.

4-[3-Allyl-4-hydroxy-5-methoxy-benzylidene)-amino]-N-(4,6-dimethyl-pyrimidin-2-yl)benzenesulfonamide (**3d**) :

Recrystallization from ethanol : C₂₃H₂₄N₄O₄S; Mol. wt. 452; yield 80%; m.p. 72 °C; colour : cremish white; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3450 (O-H), 1640 (CH=N); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ, ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (2H, m, Ar-H), 4.96 (2H, d, CH), 6.4 (1H, p, CH), 3.5 (2H, d, CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 4.2 (1H, s, SO₂NH), 3.8 (1H, s, CH), 2.8–3.0 (6H, s, CH₃). Anal. Calcd. (%) : C, 61.10; H, 5.30; N, 12.38; O, 14.14; S, 7.09.

Microbiology :

All the compounds were screened for their *in vitro*

antifungal activity at Birla Institute of Medical Research and College of Life Sciences, Gwalior, against 24 h old cultures of fungal pathogens. Antifungal activity was determined against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* using disc diffusion assay. For this sterile filter paper disc (8 mm) impregnated with fixed doses (500 µg/mL, 1000 µg/mL) of synthesized compounds under investigation were placed upon the seeded petri dishes. Similar plates were prepared for the standard drugs, the reference antifungal drug was Terbiforce. Dimethyl formamide is used as control solvent. The plates were allowed to stay for 24 h at 37 °C for bacterial strains. The zone of inhibition, observed around the disc after incubation were measured. The compounds show less activity at 500 µg/disc concentration and exhibited promising activities at 1000 µg/disc concentration, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of *in vitro* antifungal activity observed for the synthesized imine compounds through disc diffusion assay

Sr. No.	Compound	Zone of inhibition	<i>Aspergillus aureus</i>	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>
1.	1a	1	–	–
		2	16	14
2.	1b	1	–	–
		2	10	16
3.	1c	1	10	–
		2	20	12
4.	1d	1	–	–
		2	16	20
5.	2a	1	–	–
		2	10	16
6.	2b	1	–	12
		2	16	20
7.	2c	1	11	–
		2	22	16
8.	2d	1	–	–
		2	16	20
9.	3a	1	10	–
		2	16	14
10.	3b	1	–	–
		2	10	14
11.	3c	1	12	10
		2	24	20
12.	3d	1	–	–
		2	15	14
	Control (Std – Terbiforce)		28	24
	Blank (DMF)		–	–

1 = 500 µg/ml, 2 = 1000 µg/ml, (–) = No effect.

Results and discussion

In the present work 12 new compounds were synthesized. The synthetic route for the compounds is outlined in Scheme 1. Equimolar quantities of these aromatic amines and sulphonamides derivatives was reacted for the first time in presence of mild acidic condition give azomethine in good to excellent yield. All the synthesized compounds were purified by successive recrystallization using ethanol. The purity of the synthesized compounds was checked by performing TLC. The structures of the synthesized compounds were determined on the basis of their FTIR, ¹H NMR data and elemental analyzer.

The IR spectra of the synthesized compounds showed the presence azomethine group of C=N stretching bands at 1600–1690 cm⁻¹. In ¹H NMR spectra all the compounds were characterized by the presence of imino proton (CH=N) at 8.1–8.5 ppm. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Results of *in vitro* antifungal activity observed for the synthesized imine compounds through disc diffusion assay. The reference antifungal drug is Terbiforce. The fungi mould are *Aspergillus aureus* and *Aspergillus flavus*. It is observed that *Aspergillus aureus* show less to good moderate activity while *Asperilgus flavus* show good to maximum inhibition nearly in all compounds.

Conclusion

Our results encourage the synthesis of new analogs of imines to give new class of antifungal agents.

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